

Assessment of Deterministic Neutronic Methods for HALEU-fuelled Gas-Cooled Space Reactors with WIMS

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803996

ABSTRACT

High-assay low-enriched uranium (HALEU)-fuelled gas-cooled fast reactors are promising candidates for compact, long-duration space power systems. Most neutronic assessments of space reactor concepts have relied on Monte Carlo methods, while the applicability of deterministic methods are less explored despite their potential advantages for rapid design iteration and multiphysics coupling.

This study explores two space reactor designs in this category, evaluating the performance of deterministic flux-solution schemes in WIMS against detailed SERPENT reference models. Six representative core cases are explored: three isothermal uranium nitride (UN) configurations at 880 K, 1090 K, and 1300 K, and three isothermal metallic uranium-molybdenum (U-Mo) configurations at 623 K, 723 K, and 823 K. Both cores exploit high uranium-density fuels without a moderator but a beryllium oxide (BeO) reflector, resulting in an epithermal/fast neutron spectrum. Among the tested whole-core flux solutions, the WIMS RZ method with SP₃ approximation achieved the best agreement relative to SERPENT, with a mean absolute reactivity discrepancy ($|\Delta\rho|$) of 169 pcm and 157 pcm for the UN and U-Mo cores, respectively. The WIMS HEXTRIZ method also performed well considering the novelty of the designs with $|\Delta\rho|$ of 488 pcm and 559 pcm for UN and U-Mo cores, respectively. The close agreement with Monte Carlo solutions demonstrate the applicability of deterministic WIMS methods for this emerging reactor technology.

Keywords: HALEU, WIMS, deterministic methods

1. INTRODUCTION

There is growing interest in the development of compact megawatt-scale fission reactors for planetary surface power and nuclear electric propulsion (NEP) applications [1, 2]. The historic precedent is to fuel space reactors with Highly Enriched Uranium (HEU); however, non-proliferation concerns make using HEU difficult and hence the interest in High-Assay Low Enrichment Uranium (HALEU) fuel [3]. There is less experience in the development of HALEU space reactors and zero flight experience. Uranium nitride (UN) and uranium-10 wt.% molybdenum (U-10Mo) are both considered viable HALEU fuel options for space reactor applications [2]. Recent studies have highlighted renewed focus on gas-cooled and heat-pipe-cooled systems, particularly those that avoid moderator materials within the active core region. Eliminating moderation enables higher operating temperatures, which are critical for minimising radiator size and overall launch mass [2]. However, such designs still require reflectors, shifting the neutron spectrum towards epithermal.

The present work focuses on comparing deterministic neutronic methods for Xe-He gas-cooled reactor concepts designed to achieve a five-year operational lifetime in support of NEP and planetary surface

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power missions. While most studies of HALEU-fuelled micro-reactors have focused on Monte Carlo modelling, there has been relatively limited work on HALEU gas-cooled micro-reactor systems employing beryllium oxide (BeO) reflectors, which exhibit an epithermal neutron spectrum and the suitability of different deterministic methods given their ability to support rapid design iteration and future multiphysics coupling. This study investigates the applicability of deterministic flux-solution schemes in WIMS (version 11C DV3) [4], benchmarking their performance against high-fidelity SERPENT (version 2.2.2) reference models [5].

2. CORE DESIGN

Two core concepts are considered: 1) a UN pellet-fuel design based on the ALLEGRO MOX assembly [6], and 2) a U-10Mo monolithic design. Both cores employ HALEU enriched to 19.75% ^{235}U , as well as a He/Xe coolant mixture (40 g/mol) to reduce turbine size and launch mass [7].

For the UN concept the ALLEGRO assembly and fuel pin dimensions detailed by S. Cerba (2014) [6] are retained but materials are modified. UN fuel is leveraged for its high uranium density, paired with 9-Cr ODS steel cladding and wrapper for higher temperature operation. The U-10Mo monolithic design draws from the JANUS space reactor concept [8], replacing the original HEU BISO fuel embedded in graphite with U-10Mo monolithic fuel but retaining fuel element geometry. In both cases, assemblies/fuel-elements are arranged together in rings surrounded by a cylindrical BeO reflector, keeping the core height and diameter matched. SERPENT was used to establish the smallest volume design which could operate for 5 years at 3 MW_{th}. Additional core parameters are summarised in Table I, and cross sections of the two are displayed in Figure 1a. Figure 1b displays the HEXTRIZ model representation of the two cores, as discussed in Section 3.1.

Table I. Key core parameters.

Parameter	UN Core	U-10Mo Core
Fuel unit type	fuel assembly	monolithic fuel element
Fuel unit diameter (flat-to-flat)	11.1 cm	2.23 cm
Number of fuel units	37	253
Core active diameter (flat-to-flat)	77.7 cm	37.91 cm
Core outer diameter	107.7 cm	53.25 cm

For space reactors, control rods are often avoided to minimise core penetrations and reduce axial power-profile skewing, with reactivity control often served via control drums. In the present study, neither control drums nor control rods are modelled, pending further core development and optimisation.

The WIMS neutronic suite is used here to enable rapid iteration of design modifications. The code provides multiple flux-solver options and modelling features, which must be assessed to ensure accurate representation of the core physics. To test the various WIMS solution schemes, three isothermal variations of the UN core and the U-10Mo core are considered. For the UN core the three cases are: 880 K, 1090 K, and 1300 K. These represent the potential inlet, midpoint, and outlet temperatures of the core; matching the inlet/outlet temperatures of the JANUS concept [8]. In the U-10Mo case, the temperatures are 623 K, 723 K, and 823 K. The densities for the fuel, coolant, and cladding (in the UN core case) are varied at these configurations to simulate thermal expansion however, the geometry is kept fixed.

Figure 1. Cross-sections of the UN core based on the ALLEGRO assembly geometry (left), and the alternative core with hexagonal metallic U-10Mo fuel elements (right). The heterogeneous cores are displayed on top (a) and the HEXTRIZ representations are displayed the bottom (b). See section Section 3.1.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study, SERPENT is used as a point of comparison for WIMS models. Both WIMS and SERPENT were run with the ENDF/B-VII.0 nuclear data library [9]. SERPENT models were run with 200,000 neutrons per cycle with 400 active cycles and 50 inactive. Each SERPENT model was run on 20 CPU cores, whereas WIMS models were run on 1 core. All four WIMS solution scheme variations followed the sequence of modules displayed in Figure 2.

As shown in Figure 2, the calculation sequence begins with WIMSECCO, which accepts heterogeneous or homogeneous geometries and uses 1968 energy groups [10]. This fine-group structure improves accuracy by accounting for resonance self-shielding effects, which are particularly important in fast or epithermal spectrum systems. The fine-group cross sections are then condensed into the 172-group structure used in subsequent WIMS calculations.

For the heterogeneous assembly, the WIMSECCO multigroup cross sections are passed to the CACTUS(3D) module to solve for the flux distribution using the method of characteristics [10]. A network of regularly arranged tracks is spread throughout the geometry, along which a one-dimensional form of the neutron transport equation is integrated. In all cases, six azimuthal angles with a track separation of 0.05 cm and three polar angles were used, as determined through convergence studies. The whole-core CACTUSOT module is not employed here due to runtime limitations. The SMEAR module is then used

Figure 2. The solution scheme employed for the reactor designs discussed in this paper. The flux solver can be substituted for multiple different modules.

to homogenise the lattice into a combined material, preserving the reaction rates of the heterogeneous lattice.

3.1. Whole-Core Flux Solution Methods Explored

This study evaluates four flux-solution methods available in the MERLIN whole-core module: 1) RZ with the diffusion approximation; 2) RZ with the SP_3 approximation; 3) HEXTRIZ with the SP_3 approximation in 172 energy groups; and 4) HEXTRIZ with the SP_3 approximation in 33 energy groups.

MERLIN solves the multi-group eigenvalue neutron transport equation for a variety of geometries using an iterative approach. For the hexagonal lattice considered here, both diffusion and SP_3 approximations are supported.

The first MERLIN geometry investigated, the RZ model, approximates the core as concentric cylinders. The flux is solved in two dimensions (radial “R” and axial “Z”), assuming rotational symmetry and conserving the material volumes when mapping the actual core to cylindrical regions. The second geometry, HEXTRIZ, represents the core as a lattice of hexagonal blocks. This nominally allows a more accurate representation of fuel assemblies and elements. However it also necessitates that all core components be modelled hexagonally, including the reflector. Two energy group structures are investigated, using the RZ SP_3 flux solution to collapse the 172-group cross sections into 33 groups. This case is considered due to the comparatively high computational cost of HEXTRIZ, using fewer groups reduce runtime at the cost of cross section energy resolution.

The RZ models are tested against detailed heterogeneous SERPENT models with a cylindrical reflector, as seen in Figure 1a. The HEXTRIZ cores are instead tested against SERPENT cores with a matching hexagonal reflector as seen in Figure 1b, where the reflector volume is kept as close as possible to the corresponding cylindrical case.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results for the four whole-core solution schemes are displaced in Tables II to V. For all models k_{eff} is listed, as well as the WIMS model runtimes. The SERPENT model runtimes are not listed in the tables, but were ≈ 30 minutes for the UN core and ≈ 10 minutes for the U-10Mo core, using 20 CPU cores. The discrepancy in reactivity, $\Delta\rho$, measuring in pcm, has been calculated via Equation (1).

$$\Delta\rho(\text{pcm}) = 10^5 \cdot \frac{k_{\text{eff,WIMS}} - k_{\text{eff,SERPENT}}}{k_{\text{eff,WIMS}} \cdot k_{\text{eff,SERPENT}}} \quad (1)$$

To verify the SERPENT models, the cycle history was assessed, confirming that the solution converged

before the active cycles began. Additionally, the flux spectrum has been retrieved for both cores using SERPENT to establish the spectrum type (e.g. fast or epithermal), comparing to the spectrum of an example PWR core taken from Ref. [11]; all displayed together in Figure 3. The flux spectra of both cores are clearly weighted towards fast neutron energies in comparison to the PWR example. The UN core is more epithermal compared to the UMo core.

Figure 3. The flux spectrum as measured in SERPENT of the UN core, the UMo core, and an example PWR design. The flux is measured in arbitrary units and is normalised.

Table II. Core variation benchmark using the MERLIN RZ solution in WIMS with the diffusion approximation. Includes the WIMS runtimes using 1 CPU.

Core Variation	SERPENT k_{eff}	WIMS k_{eff}	runtime (mm:ss)	$\Delta\rho$ (pcm)
UN 880 K	1.02774(8)	1.02011	01:48	-728(7)
UN 1090 K	1.02542(8)	1.01820	01:48	-691(7)
UN 1300 K	1.02330(8)	1.01659	01:47	-645(8)
U-10Mo 623 K	1.02767(7)	1.01214	01:04	-1493(7)
U-10Mo 723 K	1.02491(7)	1.00919	01:09	-1519(7)
U-10Mo 823 K	1.02198(8)	1.00628	01:06	-1526(7)

The MERLIN RZ models with diffusion approximation had the fastest runtimes of all methods, however with significant absolute mean reactivity discrepancy with SERPENT; $|\Delta\rho| = 688$ pcm for the UN core, and 1513 pcm for the U-10Mo core. Switching to the SP₃ approximation significantly reduces the discrepancy to $|\Delta\rho| = 169$ pcm and 157 pcm respectively, without significant runtime increase.

With HEXTRIZ, the range of $\Delta\rho$ was similar across all models. When modelled with the default 172

Table III. Core variation benchmark using the MERLIN RZ solution in WIMS with the SP_3 approximation. Includes the WIMS runtimes using 1 CPU.

Core Variation	SERPENT k_{eff}	WIMS k_{eff}	runtime (mm:ss)	$\Delta\rho$ (pcm)
UN 880 K	1.02774(8)	1.02535	02:40	-227(7)
UN 1090 K	1.02542(8)	1.02362	02:25	-171(7)
UN 1300 K	1.02330(8)	1.02216	02:26	-109(8)
U-10Mo 623 K	1.02767(7)	1.02601	02:47	-157(7)
U-10Mo 723 K	1.02491(7)	1.02320	02:57	-163(7)
U-10Mo 823 K	1.02198(8)	1.02042	04:23	-150(7)

Table IV. Core variation benchmark using the MERLIN HEXTRIZ solution in WIMS with 172 groups, compared to an equivalent SERPENT core. Includes the WIMS runtimes using 1 CPU.

Core Variation	SERPENT k_{eff}	WIMS k_{eff}	runtime (mm:ss)	$\Delta\rho$ (pcm)
UN 880 K	1.03552(8)	1.02735	11:52	-768(7)
UN 1090 K	1.03319(8)	1.02636	10:45	-644(8)
UN 1300 K	1.03142(8)	1.02548	11:32	-562(7)
U-10Mo 623 K	1.03427(8)	1.02943	40:22	-455(7)
U-10Mo 723 K	1.02126(8)	1.02658	41:26	-442(7)
U-10Mo 823 K	1.02853(8)	1.02381	41:05	-448(7)

Table V. Core variation benchmark using the MERLIN HEXTRIZ solution in WIMS with 33 groups, compared to an equivalent SERPENT core. Includes the WIMS runtimes using 1 CPU.

Core Variation	SERPENT k_{eff}	WIMS k_{eff}	runtime (mm:ss)	$\Delta\rho$ (pcm)
UN 880 K	1.03552(8)	1.02945	03:19	-569(7)
UN 1090 K	1.03319(8)	1.02813	03:05	-476(8)
UN 1300 K	1.03142(8)	1.02699	02:59	-418(7)
U-10Mo 623 K	1.03427(8)	1.02827	05:30	-564(7)
U-10Mo 723 K	1.02126(8)	1.02542	05:24	-552(7)
U-10Mo 823 K	1.02853(8)	1.02261	07:36	-562(7)

groups the UN and U-10Mo cores exhibited mean absolute discrepancies of $|\overline{\Delta\rho}| = 658$ and 448 pcm respectively, whereas with 33 groups this was $|\overline{\Delta\rho}| = 488$ and 559 pcm. A slight increase in agreement was seen with SERPENT when the energy groups were condensed in the UN case, however the opposite was true for the U-10Mo core. Such discrepancies are reasonable in feasibility studies of relatively novel systems and material combinations [12], however further research is desirable to reduce this discrepancy. The main advantage demonstrated by condensing to 33 groups was in the runtime, reducing from a maximum ≈ 40 minute runtime down to ≈ 7 minutes, without significant alteration of $\Delta\rho$.

Across all test cases for k_{eff} calculations, WIMS RZ models with SP_3 showed the best agreement with

SERPENT, with fast runtimes. HEXTRIZ also proved capable of reaching acceptable levels of agreement with SERPENT, with reactivity differences close to those seen in other similar studies [8, 13].

The SERPENT models took approximately 30 minutes to run each for the UN core, or 10 minutes for the U-10Mo core. When calculating power profiles, SERPENT runtimes will necessarily increase beyond this as the accuracy depends on the number of neutrons in the volume relevant to the measurement. In contrast, WIMS runtimes will not increase for such purposes. It is also worth noting that with the tested methods, WIMS calculations were performed on a single CPU, providing a further runtime advantage where available computational power is limited or there is a need to run many cases in parallel.

5. FUTURE WORK

Future work will extend this analysis to the WIMS GroupMONK method — a hybrid approach that applies the MONK Monte Carlo solver to the whole-core using the homogenised material regions generated by WIMS. This will provide a useful intermediate comparison between deterministic and fully Monte Carlo methods. An additional case of interest would be to use cross-sections generated from MONK within a deterministic transport method. The CACTUSOT solver, excluded here due to anticipated runtime constraints, will also be revisited with additional energy-group condensation. Another key extension will be to investigate fuel depletion, comparing method performance over burnup.

Design optimisation will follow, which will focus on refining the core aspect ratio to balance coolant pressure drop and neutron leakage, and on shaping the power distribution via enrichment zoning. The reactivity coefficients will then be determined and the performance of control drums for reactivity control will be assessed, including potential launch failure scenarios. The solution scheme will be reassessed and potentially modified once control drums are included, as strong absorbers may impact the schemes viability.

The established RZ SP₃ scheme will serve as the basis for subsequent reactor optimisation and multi-physics coupling. Power distributions derived from this scheme will support finite element structural performance modelling, as well as temperature-dependent feedback studies using the ARTHUR and CAMELOT modules available in WIMS.

6. CONCLUSION

WIMS provides a viable framework for fast whole-core modelling of small, HALEU-fuelled, gas-cooled epithermal/fast reactors. Two core designs were modelled at three isothermal temperature/density configurations. The first core utilised UN pin-type fuel, and the second utilising U-10Mo monolithic fuel elements. Among the MERLIN solution schemes, the RZ geometry with SP₃ approximation showed the best agreement with SERPENT, with an average reactivity difference of 169 pcm for the UN core and 157 pcm for the U-10Mo core. The HEXTRIZ method also performed acceptably; the 33-group configuration reduced runtimes compared to the 172-group case while yielding a reactivity discrepancy of 488 pcm and 553 pcm for the UN and U-10Mo cores respectively; a minimal difference relative to the 172-group case. In general, WIMS tended to predict a lower k_{eff} than SERPENT. Overall, the results indicate that WIMS models with RZ geometry and SP₃ approximation are suitable for rapid design iteration and analysis of small HALEU-fuelled gas-cooled systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support from the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) and the United Kingdom National Nuclear Laboratory (UKNNL) through the SATURN Centre for Doctoral Training (award EP/50/22295/1) for C. Barnes, and from the Royal Society through an Industry Fellowship (INF \R1 \221061) for A. Peakman.

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